

Adaptive Public Art and Pavilion for vibrant public life in Arctic area

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INTRODUCTION

Kiruna is the northernmost town in Sweden. There is a plan to move the old Kiruna city and then build a new Kiruna city. When we interviewed the inhabitants, they expressed the wish for meeting places. The green challenge is that how this public space is adaptive to the summer and extreme long and cold winter and satisfies the demand and use of the inhabitants here. The public art here should offer the inhabitants a flexible space for their public life, namely a warm place in winter and an attractive space for diverse activities. This project is to find possible attractive public art that could be applied in this space both in winter and summer and cater to the local needs.

THEORY & METHODOLOGY

There are different ways for the public life study. In 1971, Whyte started his pioneering project, *The Street Life Project*, in which he implemented basic observational studies of the human social activities in the small public space, sometimes with a time-lapse camera. *The Social Life of Small Urban Spaces* (Whyte, 1980) illustrates vividly the reasons why some places are more attractive to people and others are not. Besides, when observing the pedestrian behaviors in the traditional European cities, Gehl “add a dimension that interviews with people about the reason for their being in the city” (Gehl & Svarre, 2013). They build up a method and tool system for public life studies in the book *How to Study Public Life*. In this project, we interviewed several inhabitants here to get a clear picture of the local needs for the public life here. Also the main effort was made to observe the public life and human behavior here. Data of the demography is collected and analyzed for design.

RESULT

Interviews shows that people want an outdoor dancing place in winter and they want to build a close relationship with the young people in the meeting place. Besides, the inhabitants love to hang out in winter and can stand the temperature. When searing for similar programs and adaptive designs, we find a lot of interesting information and reference projects. In the context of Kiruna, a wooden pavilion, with a warming hut is a nice place for dancing in winter and a flexible open space for diverse activities in summer. In addition, enlightened by excellent ideas of public art from artists, we also like to apply light art in Kiruna.

CONCLUSION

The adaptability of public art and pavilion can create a more dynamic and attractive public space for potential public life. Not only is the technology important for the public space design, but also the inhabitants’ demand and their use of the space.